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Prof. Maria-Helen E. Ekah & Jacob, Uwakmfon Effiong

A Study of Mechanical Errors in Selected Secondary School Students' Essays in Uyo Metropolis

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Abstract

This paper examines mechanical errors in selected secondary school students' essays in Uyo metropolis. The subjects of the study consist of fifty (50) junior secondary three (JS3) students learning English as a second language. A purposive sampling technique was used to select ten (10) students from three private secondary schools and two government secondary schools, making a total of fifty (50) students. The data for the investigation were collected using essay writing, which required the subjects to write an essay on one out of the four topics provided. The theoretical framework used was error analysis, which also aided in the qualitative analyses. The written compositions were examined for mechanic errors, which include capitalisation and punctuation mark errors. The analysis revealed that most of the subjects in the schools under study made more errors in capitalisation, followed by apostrophes and full stops. The findings of this study indicate that the mechanics of English are challenging to junior secondary school students and second language learners of English in Uyo Metropolis.

Keywords: Mechanics, Error Analysis, Capitalisation, Fullstop, Apostrophe

1. Introduction

Language is a system of rules consisting of phonological, morphological, syntactic and semantic components. Any native speaker-hearer of a language can be competent in all of these except mechanical rules because they involve writing, which is one of the four language skills. These skills are learned, not acquired, even in a first language situation. The source also states that one of the writing rules of English is that every sentence should begin with a capital letter and end with a full stop if it is a declarative sentence. On the other hand, if the sentence is interrogative, it should end with a question mark; if exclamatory, it ends with an exclamation mark.

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The British colonial government introduced the English language in Nigeria through trade, religion and the establishment of schools where the language was taught and is still being taught. Despite this long history, many learners still struggle to use English with the same level of competence as native speakers, especially in speaking and writing. Ekah (2018) explains that language skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) comprise oral language behaviour and written language behaviour. Speaking and writing are productive skills while listening and reading are comprehension skills.

Stott and Chapman (2001), cited in Ekah (2018), state that between the capital letter and the full stop, or any other terminal mark, lies a whole lot of things like spaces, punctuation, lexical categories, and phrasal categories as well as grammatical units, each entering into a relationship with the other. To have good writing, a writer must be able to organise and construct a good sentence, choose appropriate vocabulary and organise the sentences properly following grammatical and mechanical rules of English. The appropriate use of grammatical and mechanical rules enhances the meaning of a sentence. It can resolve any misunderstanding between the writer and the reader.

However, in second language learning situations, learners commit a lot of errors. This is normal because learners cannot learn without making errors. Errors can help learners discover where they default and to make corrections. Some learners often commit mechanical errors while writing. This happens because most learners do not pay attention to the mechanics of English, such as spellings, the use of capital letters and punctuation marks when writing. They also lack the knowledge of rules guiding the use of punctuation marks and capital letters in an appropriate way.

The mechanics of English deserve serious attention from all users of the language, especially learners of English as a second language. Incorrect use of capital letters, wrong spellings, and inappropriate punctuation marks can lead to communication breakdown and unacceptable written expression. Many second-language learners face difficulties when writing essays in English, and one of the major challenges identified is the misuse of mechanical features. This paper investigates the causes and sources of the difficulties encountered by English bilinguals in written communication, especially among junior secondary school students in Uyo Metropolis.

Data for the research was drawn from the essays of fifty (50) junior secondary three (JS3) students in three (3) private and two (2) government secondary schools in Uyo Metropolis. Ten (10) JS3 students from different arms of the five schools were

purposively selected for the study. The data were classified according to the types of mechanical errors identified in the essays. The researcher analysed the data using error analysis.

2. Writing

Written language has rules that must be followed to produce effective writing. Good writing occurs when the reader clearly understands the information or ideas being communicated. Writing is one of the three modes of linguistic expression and communication, alongside speaking and signing. It involves the consideration of relationships among the elements of writing (relational aspect), the use of strategies for developing and communicating ideas (strategic aspect), and the use of available discursive repertoire (textual aspect) (Schmitt, 2010).

Ekah (2015) states that writing a word takes more time than saying the same word and that every word has parts except the words "I" and "a". According to the source, all essential parts of a word must be adequately represented orthographically because the omission of even one letter may change the meaning of the word entirely. For example, in the word "thank", if the letter "h" is omitted, it becomes "tank", which is entirely different in meaning. Similarly, inserting "h" into "tank" changes the intended meaning.

Langan (2013) further explains how challenging writing can be by stating that many people find it difficult to engage in the intense and active thinking that clear writing demands. He notes that it can be frustrating to transfer thoughts and feelings from the mind into words. This reflects the experience of many people, especially learners, when carrying out writing tasks. According to him, competent writing comes through hard work, determination, effort, and persistence. However, he adds that writing is a skill that can be mastered if one is willing to put in the necessary effort.

Writing is the process of expressing meaning through written symbols. A writer sends a message, and a reader receives it. An effective writer considers the reader (audience), while an effective reader considers the writer (author). Writing and reading therefore rely on and strengthen each other. There is a strong relationship between reading and writing because one influences and enriches the other. Henry (2011) remarks that the more one reads, the more one knows, and the more one has to write about. The source also explains that through reading, a writer gains new vocabulary, different perspectives on a topic, additional facts, supporting details for arguments, various ways of applying writing techniques such as punctuation use, creative expressions, sentence

construction, idea organisation, and methods of opening and closing an essay.

2.1 Mechanics of English

The mechanics of English are the essential elements on which effective writing is built and which help achieve correct usage and proper understanding of a written text (Eka, 2004). These mechanics include capitalisation, spelling, and punctuation marks.

Murthy (2018) defines punctuation as the correct use of stops in a sentence. Henry (2011) explains that capitalisation refers to writing letters, and sometimes entire words, in uppercase form. The most common use of capitalisation is writing the first letter of a word in uppercase while the remaining letters are in lowercase, especially to indicate the beginning of a sentence. Eka (2004) further explains that capitalisation refers to the process of using capital letters at specific points in writing.

Capital letters play a very important role in English discourse. They serve as mechanical tools that help the writer achieve clarity of expression, concrete meaning, and logical thought. When used properly, capital letters provide clear reference points and meaningful links between ideas expressed in sentences and paragraphs. According to Josiah and Nwoke (2017), the major functions of capital letters include: (a) marking the beginning of sentences and direct speeches; (b) indicating proper nouns; and (c) denoting abbreviations, among others.

In a paper titled *Students' Errors in Using Capital Letter and Punctuation in Writing a Descriptive Text*, Rahman, Sofyan, and Gusnadi (2017) investigated students' errors in the use of capital letters and punctuation marks in descriptive writing, as well as the causes of these errors. Their findings showed that the most common capitalisation errors occurred in writing the names of places and persons. In the use of commas, students made errors before or after coordinating conjunctions and also placed commas at the end of sentences. For apostrophes, many students omitted letters in contractions. The study also found that carelessness was the major cause of these errors. The researchers concluded that students need to be more careful while engaging in any form of writing.

Ramos, Cadio, Barabat, and Dilag (2022), in a study on the most frequent capitalisation errors of Thai learners of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in writing short responses and book reviews, observed that writing is a challenging task for EFL learners. They recommended that students should pay attention to the four major writing conventions: punctuation, spelling, grammar, and capitalisation. They also

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stated that when learners understand and recognise the errors they make, their writing ability can improve significantly. Their findings revealed that failure to capitalise proper nouns and adjectives was the most frequent error in short responses, while failure to capitalise the first letter of a sentence ranked highest in book reviews. The researchers suggested that greater emphasis should be placed on these identified errors. They stressed that such errors are not merely mistakes but challenges that require attention. They also noted that addressing these writing challenges is an important task for teachers of English as a second language. These reviewed works are relevant to this paper because this study also examines mechanical errors among selected Junior Secondary School Three (JSS3) students in Uyo Metropolis.

Mohammed, Masoud, and Al-Deen (2021) conducted a study on punctuation, capitalisation, and spelling errors in learners' essays. The study aimed to analyse the types of errors that occurred, determine the frequency of each type, and examine whether there were statistically significant differences based on gender. The researchers analysed the errors quantitatively using Na-ngam's (2005) framework with the help of Excel software and the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The findings showed that learners committed errors in all three areas, with a total of 967 errors recorded. Capitalisation errors were the most frequent, accounting for 387 errors (40%), followed by spelling errors with 292 errors (30%), while punctuation errors were the least frequent, with 288 errors (30%). Statistically, the study showed no significant difference among these error types. It revealed that learners still face difficulties in the proper use of orthographic features. This study is relevant to the present research because it also focuses on learners' essays and examines similar aspects of mechanical errors.

3. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical model adopted for this work is Error Analysis (EA). Error analysis is an approach in second language analysis introduced by Corder (1967) as a response to the inadequacies of the contrastive analysis (CA) approach. It emerged as a diagnostic tool to evaluate and understand the linguistic competence of second language (L2) learners by identifying, describing, classifying, and systematically analysing their errors (Otagburuagu, Ogenyi and Ezema, 2013, cited in Nzerem and Bob, 2019). According to Richard (2002), cited in Nzerem and Bob (2019), the aim of error analysis is to identify the strategies that learners use in language learning, while also paying attention to the approaches and strategies employed in the teaching and learning process. Another aim

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is to identify the causes of learners' errors and, finally, to obtain information on areas of difficulties in language learning which will help in adequate preparation of the teaching materials. Corder (1967) emphasises that errors are not merely signs of linguistic deficiency but are insightful indicators of the developmental stage in a learner's interlanguage.

Error analysts collect and identify data from the target language to differentiate errors from mistakes. Errors are classified according to types such as omission, addition, substitution, or related word order. It is also classified into global and local errors. Global errors are those that affect the whole structure of a sentence, thereby rendering the sentence unintelligible. Local errors affect a particular part of the sentence; it does not lead to extinguishing the meaning of the sentence (Akidi, 2016).

When the form of a language of a learner deviates from or violates the rules of a target language, there is an error (Agbedo, 2015, cited in Ekah, 2018). This shows that the inability of a language learner to acquire the rules of the language learnt can result in blunders. Corder (1981) states that an error is a learner's language form of writing that deviates from, or violates, a target language rule. The source also says that those rules may be used only in formal contexts, not in informal discourse, or they may fit speakers from some geographic regions where the language is spoken. While native speakers make unsystematic performance errors (like slips of the tongue) from time to time, or shift from formal to informal grammatical patterns in informal contexts, second language learners make errors that no native speaker ever makes, errors that are systematic violations of the linguistic patterns to which they have been exposed, which gives information about the learner's current knowledge of the rules of the language being learnt.

The theory states that after exposure to the target language, learners would form hypotheses about the nature of certain rules. They would then test their hypotheses when producing the target language utterances. Learners would modify their hypotheses about the nature of the target language rules so that their utterances increasingly conformed to the target language, ultimately leading to improved accuracy and fluency in their language use. According to Corder (1967), the following are the stages involved in error analysis: data collection; identification of errors; classification of errors; description of errors; explanation of errors; evaluation and correction of errors. This paper applies these tenets in its analysis of mechanical errors of selected Junior Secondary School 3 (JSS3) students in Uyo Metropolis.

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4. Research Methodology

The respondents were given four essay topics; from which they were to choose one to write on. The essay type of written work was used for data collection because it is a task that gives the students room for self-expression, choice of vocabulary and the benefit of presenting facts clearly in written English. The topics consisted of an expository essay entitled 'The Menace of Fake Drugs in the Society, The State of Nigeria's Economy,' descriptive essay entitled 'The World of My Dream' and a narrative essay entitled 'My Unforgettable Trip'

The data generated were subsequently analysed and discussed. Samples of the sentences and vocabulary items selected were analysed using frequency count of observed errors. These were calculated in simple percentages to ascertain the errors that were prevalent in the written composition of the JS3 respondents. Error analysis was adopted for the qualitative analysis of the data. The researcher examined the errors of the students' mechanical accuracy in terms of: capitalisation and punctuation marks. The distribution of schools for collection of data is presented in Table 4. Each school is represented by an alphabet lettered A-E. The letters are used to number the scripts of the respondents in each school which sums up to fifty. The lettering is for the analysis of the data.

Table 4: Distribution of Schools for Collection of Data

	Name of School (JS3 Class)	School Type	Male	Female	Total
A	Heritage College, Uyo	Private	5	5	10
B	Evangel High School, Uyo	Private	5	5	10
C	Christian Secondary Commercial School, Uyo	Government	5	5	10
D	Uwakmfonabasi International School, Uyo	Private	5	5	10
E	Community Secondary School, Aka Offot, Uyo	Government	5	5	10
	Total				50

5. Data Presentation and Analysis of Mechanical Errors

5.1 Wrong Capitalisation

An error occurs when words are poorly capitalised in sentences. Capitalisation is a fundamental component of mechanics in writing, and its misuse may significantly affect the clarity, formality, and accuracy of written communication. The following data were extracted from the respondents' written essays.

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Table 5.1: Capitalisation Errors

S/N	Error Identification	Error Correction
1	My Dreams are widely what I hope to see. A1	My dreams are largely what I hope to see. A1
2	Basically the announcement of the trip started on thursday by my parents. A3	Basically, the announcement of the trip by my parents started on Thursday . A3
3	fake drugs price are subsidised thus attract customers from low background. A4	Fake drug prices are reduced thus attracting customers from low income background. A4
4	as we were going when we reached odukpani junction the car over heated. A6	As we were going, when we reached Odukpani junction, the car over heated. A6
5	... I realised that I was given a project on the species of animals in biology . A10	... I realised that I was given a project on the species of animals in Biology . A10
6	We visited the Ibom e-library and I was fascinated at the infrastructure both within and outside. B11	We visited the Ibom E-Library and I was fascinated at the infrastructure, both within and outside. B11
7	My unforgettable trip was a trip of a day that I wont forget In my life. B14	My unforgettable trip was a trip of a day that I won't forget in my life. B14
8	It was a bright sunny sunday noon after sunday service. B16	It was a bright sunny Sunday noon after Sunday service. B16
9	He took me to banana island . B17	He took me to Banana Island . B17
10	I decided to spent my christmas holiday without my parent so I travelled to Benin. B18	I decided to spend my Christmas holiday without my parents, so I travelled to Benin. B18
11	we left in the morning using our car. C21	We left in the morning using our car. C21
12	It was on a Summer Sunday Evening C23	It was on a summer Sunday evening C23
13	The day was friday , 20 th january , 2025.... C29	The day was Friday , 20 th January , 2025.... C29
14	I enter the plane at the ilorin Airport.... D31	I entered the plane at the Ilorin Airport.... D31
15	...we knew that the trip was going to be a long, fun and Interesting one. D32	...we knew that the trip was going to be long, fun and interesting . D32
16	The state of Nigeria economy Is at a very bad stage.... D34	The state of Nigeria's economy is very bad.... D34
17	The government do not care for the welfare of the people because of the sleffish Interest In them. D34	The government does not care for the welfare of the people because of the selfish interest of government officials . D34
18	when we got into the place It was so cold. D36	When we got into the place, it was very cold. D36
19	It was a normal saturday morning at home.... D38	It was a normal Saturday morning at home.... D38
20	moreover the distance was too long. D39	Moreover , the distance was too long. D39
21	we pack all our loads Into the car. E41	We packed all our loads into the car. E41
22	I was so Impress that I really wanted to learn more about drones. E41	I was so impressed that I really wanted to learn more about drones. E41

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- 23 I and my brother went to the comfort zoo at **kurudu**. E50 My brother and I went to the comfort zoo at **Kurudu**. E50

5.1.1 Capitalisation of Non-Proper Nouns

Common nouns, verbs, prepositions, adjectives and pronouns within sentences were capitalised without justification, indicating mechanical inconsistency. This reflects an observed trend in digital and informal writing contexts, where users apply capitalisation to create impact, emphasis and foregrounding effects. Students transfer this habit inappropriately into academic writing, as the following errors show:

- i. My **Dreams** are widely what I hope to see. (A1)
- ii. My unforgettable trip was a trip of a day that I won't forget **In** my life. (B14)
- iii. It was on a **Summer Sunday Evening**. (C23)
- iv. ...we knew that the trip was going to be a long, fun and **Interesting** one. (D32)
- v. The state of Nigeria economy **Is** at a very bad stage.... (D34)
- vi. **when** we got into the place **It** was so cold. (D36)
- vii. we pack all our loads **Into** the car. (E41)

The following words: 'dreams', 'in', 'summer', 'evening', 'interesting', 'is', 'it', 'into' are not proper nouns since they are not names of specific persons, places, institutions, countries etc., which are normally begun with capital letters irrespective of the position in the sentence. The subjects committed the error of capitalising them in sentences.

5.1.2 Improper Capitalisation of Proper Nouns

Capitalisation is used for proper nouns such as names of places and people, days of the week, months of the year, school subjects, organisations and festive periods, etc. However, the subjects failed to capitalise the following proper nouns in their essays:

1. **as** we were going when we reached **odukpani** junction the car over heated. (Script A6)
2. He took me to **banana island**. (Script B17)
3. I enter the plane at the **ilorin** Airport.... (Script D31)
4. I and my brother went to the comfort zoo at **kurudu**. (Script E50)
5. Basically the announcement of the trip started on **thursday** by my parents. (Script A3)
6. It was a bright sunny **sunday** noon after **sunday** service. (Script B16)

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7. The day was **friday**, 20th **january**, 2025.... (Script **C29**)
8. It was a normal **saturday** morning at home.... (Script **D38**)
9. ... I realised that I was given a project on the species of animals in **biology**. (Script **A10**)
10. I decided to spent my **christmas** holiday without my parent so I travelled to Benin. (Script **B18**)

It is observed that sentence (1) begins with a small letter while “Odukpani” which is the name of a place starts with a small letter. Banana Island, Ilorin and Kaduna are names of places. Thursday, Sunday, Friday, and Saturday are days of the week, while Biology is a school subject and Christmas holiday is a festive period. Therefore, all should start with initial capitalisation but the subjects used lower cases in the samples.

5.1.3 Beginning Sentences with Small Letters

Another aspect of capitalisation errors found among the subjects is beginning sentences with small letters which is a very fundamental error in written English. The words 'fake' in script **A4**, 'as' in script **A6**, 'we' in script **C21**, 'when' in script **D36** (number 21), and 'moreover' in script **D39**, in the sample sentences were wrongly represented. The extracts are presented as follows:

- i. **fake** drugs price are subsidised thus attract customers from low background. (**A4**)
- ii. **as** we were going when we reached odukpani junction the car over heated. (**A6**)
- iii. **we** left in the morning using our car. (**C21**)
- iv. **when** we got into the place It was so cold. (**D36**)
- v. **moreover**, the distance was too long. (**D39**)
- vi. **we** pack all our loads Into the car. (**E41**)

The error is caused by the carelessness of the students because beginning a sentence with capital letters is one of the simplest rules of capitalisation frequently taught to learners right from the primary school level. The rule states that graphologically, a sentence begins with a capital letter and ends with a full stop (Ekah, 2018).

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5.2 Wrong use of Punctuation Marks (Full-Stop and Apostrophe)

Also observed in the data collected were errors in the use of punctuation marks such as fullstop and apostrophe. The first under focus is the use of fullstop.

5.2.1 Omission of Sentence-Final Punctuation (Full Stop)

It is a graphological rule in English that a sentence starts with a capital letter and ends with a fullstop unless it is an interrogative or exclamatory sentence (Ekah, 2018). The violation of this rule causes errors in writing as observed in the following samples from the subjects:

Table 5.2: Full Stop Errors

S/N	Error Identification	Error Correction
1	We woke up very early on the agreed date A2	We woke up very early on the agreed date. A2
2	We prepared, packed our bags, unfortunately when we got into the car my dad noticed the fuel was leaking A6	We prepared and packed our bags, Unfortunately, when we got into the car, my dad noticed the fuel was leaking. A6
3	I was so happy I thanked him so much B17	I was so happy. I thanked him so much. B17

The subjects did not indicate fullstops at the end of the sentences in scripts **A2**, **A6** and **B17**. These errors were caused by lack of attention to the punctuation mark rule for using a full stop. In script **A6**, the respondent combined two independent clauses using only commas without a final punctuation. Also, in script **B17**, there is an omission of a full stop between the two independent clauses. These omissions result in run-on or fused sentences, or what is called a 'comma splice', where two sentences are combined without clear separation. These omissions reflect a limited awareness of basic punctuation rules at sentence boundaries. L2 learners often neglect punctuation because they rely heavily on speech rhythms that do not always translate to written form. This error may be traced to writing instruction that overlooks the mechanics of final punctuation.

5.2.2 Apostrophe

This is a punctuation mark that shows possession and is used for the contraction of words. When it is not properly used, an error occurs in writing as in the following extracts:

Table 5.3: Apostrophe Errors

S/N	Error Identification	Error Correction
1	Thats the fun of it. A2	That's the fun of it. A2
2	We were'nt pleased at all by what he had said.... A7	We weren't pleased at all by what he had said.... A7
3	My unforgettable trip was a trip of a day that I wont forget In my life. B14	My unforgettable trip was a trip of a day that I won't forget in my life. B14
4	I couldnt do it but my dad showed and assited me. B20	I couldn't do it but my dad showed up and assisted me. B20
5	They loaded my things in the drivers boot and left. C24	They loaded my things in the driver's boot and left. C24
6	The state of Nigeria economy Is at a very bad stage.... D34	The state of Nigeria's economy is very bad.... D34

The subjects committed errors in the use of apostrophes by omitting the punctuation mark in words that should show possession and contraction, as in 'that's', 'weren't', 'won't', and 'couldn't', as opposed to 'that's', 'weren't', 'won't', 'couldn't', 'driver's', and 'Nigeria's'. This is a very serious error mostly because they occur correctly in speech but wrongly in writing. These errors arise from the subjects' inability to distinguish between possessive forms and contractions, which are often not differentiated in speech.

5.4 Frequency of Errors of Mechanics

Table 5.4 shows the percentage frequency of the three variables under errors of mechanics. Each of the error types is identified in all the fifty scripts to arrive at a total number of occurrences. The relative frequency of the occurrence of each was then calculated to arrive at the percentage frequency as seen in the table below.

Table 5.4 - Frequency Distribution of Errors of Mechanics in Students' Essays

S/N	Variables	Total Number of Errors	% Frequency
1	Capitalisation	44	36.7%
2	Fullstop	36	30%
3	Apostrophe	40	33.3%
	Total	120	100

From the fifty scripts, capitalisation errors amounted to 36.7% (44), which is considered the most frequent error, followed by apostrophe errors, which amounted to 33.3% (40), and fullstop errors, which amounted to 30% (36). Capitalisation errors constitute 36.7

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percent out of the three variables under the errors of mechanics. The total number of errors in the designated areas of investigation is one hundred and twenty errors.

6. Discussion of Findings

Errors of mechanics, especially punctuation marks and capitalisation, were prevalent and disruptive to meaning in the subjects' essays. Many students failed to punctuate sentence boundaries properly, thereby leading to run-on, fused or fragmented sentences. Capitalisation was inconsistently applied, while areas often capitalised were those not capitalised in words and sentences. The subjects were very poor in the use of full stops. Not applying full stops at appropriate points to indicate sentence boundaries was identified. This brings about the issues of coherence and poor interpretation of meaning. The essence of communication is meaningful expression, but when meaning is not communicated, the whole essence of speaking or writing is defeated.

An apostrophe is built into words, and as tiny as the mark appears, it contributes significantly to proper writing and understanding. Most of the subjects did not give attention to its use. This may be traced to the fact that they write the way they speak, which is inappropriate and unacceptable in writing. All the areas of errors highlighted reflect typological neglect as well as poor knowledge of writing convention. Proper teaching of handwriting will help to curb the challenge of poor use of capital letters. Intensive drills on essay writing where the scripts are corrected, returned to the students and the errors and their sources discussed in the class as feedback by the teacher will help to curb a lot of the writing errors highlighted, like the use of apostrophes. Most of the errors in apostrophes are due to laziness by the learners who sometimes see inserting an apostrophe in a word as a disruption of the process of writing the word. Mechanics are not peripheral elements of writing but an integral part because they contribute to clarity of meaning and reflect on the writer's personality and level of competence in the language.

In conclusion, an integrated approach to teaching writing where grammar and mechanics are taught as a cohesive unit can help bridge this gap. Since the rules of written language are strict, it is essential for students to have a full grasp of the mechanical rules of the English language in addition to grammar rules for holistic learning. The focus on the content and creativity in the generation of ideas to tackle the given topics should be extended to how the ideas can be well represented in consonance with writing rules of English too.

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